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Research Article

**SAFETY OF TRANS ARTERIAL BASED THERAPY FOR
HCC IN PATIENTS WHO UNDERWENT ERCP
PROCEDURE: A SINGLE CENTER EXPERIENCE**¹Abdullah Ayesh AlMutairi, ¹Naif AbdulAziz AlAnizi,¹Faisal Ali AlAsmari, ²Yousof Al Zahrani¹College of Medicine, King Saud bin Abdulaziz University for Health Sciences, Riyadh,
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Abdullah Specialist Children's Hospital (KASCH) & King AbdulAziz Medical City
(KAMC)**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Purpose: retrospectively evaluate patients with a history of ERCP who had the hepatic abscess or cholangitis following TACE or TARE.

material and method: It was retrospective chart review study of patients who underwent TACE or TARE after ERCP procedure at the tertiary center, at King Abdulaziz Medical City, between May 2010 and December 2018.

Results:

A total of nine patients that had undergone TACE or TARE after ERCP were identified. The study includes seven male and two female. The mean age of patient is 64.

Five of patients underwent TACE and four patients underwent TARE. The right common femoral artery was punctured under ultrasound guidance followed by placement of 5-F vascular sheath in all the cases. Cholangitis was noted in two male patients and hepatic abscess was not found. Based on our finding, one-year survival rate is increased in patients who undergo TACE or TARE.

Conclusion:

cholangitis and hepatic abscess are rare to complication after TACE or TARE procedure in patient with history of ERCP despite other co-morbidities.

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INTRODUCTION:

Liver cancer is the fifth most widespread cancer in male, the seventh most widespread cancer in female and the third most common mortality cancer in worldwide.¹ The most common type of liver cancer is hepatic cell carcinoma (HCC).² The appropriate treatment modality of HCC is chosen based on Barcelona Clinic Liver Cancer (BCLC). The Barcelona Clinic Liver Cancer (BCLC) staging system combines tumor characteristics and performance status with liver function and links them to evidence based therapeutic options. It is the core for the European and the American HCC management guidelines.³ Moreover, there are many different treatment modalities of HCC. These includes surgery, liver transplant, percutaneous ethanol injection (PEI), molecularly targeted therapies (eg, sorafenib), cryoablation, radiation therapy, stereotactic radiotherapy, systemic chemotherapy, and trans arterial based therapy.⁴

The transarterial based therapy is an appropriate treatment for BCLC stage B.⁵ There are three major transarterial method of HCC treatment: Blind embolization [transarterial embolization (TAE)], transarterial chemoembolization and transarterial radioembolization.⁶

Transarterial embolization (TAE) is a procedure which catheter inserted into the hepatic artery that injects embolizing agents to block blood flow to the tumor without infusion of chemotherapeutic or radiotherapeutic agents.⁷ Furthermore, transarterial chemoembolization (TACE) is minimally invasive procedure in which the blood supply to a tumor is embolized after cytotoxic agent is injected into blood vessels near the tumor.⁷ Contraindications of TACE include decompensated cirrhosis, replacement of both lobes with tumor, extrahepatic metastases, a tumor size larger than 10 cm, severely reduced portal vein flow, untreated varices with risk of bleeding, and bile duct occlusion.⁸

Transarterial radioembolization (TARE) is done by injecting radioactive isotope Yttrium-90 and embolic molecules. This technique allows injecting a higher dose of radiation to a local area, without targeting a large volume of healthy tissue in the body to the radiation.⁹ The criteria for selecting patients suitable for radioembolization have been set by a medical team consisting of professionals from interventional radiology, nuclear medicine, radiation oncology, medical and surgical fields.⁹ For instance, Patients who are not suitable to surgical resection or TACE and have a life expectancy more than three months are considered for TARE.¹⁰ However, the contraindications of TARE are irreversible total serum bilirubin greater

than 2 mg/dl, excessive tumor size with poor hepatic function, and a compromised portal vein.⁸

The complication of TACE and TARE are same.¹² The most common complication is post embolization syndrome consisting of fever, nausea, abdominal pain, and vomiting. However, there are extreme complications that can happened in rare cases which includes ischemic hepatitis, pancreatitis, bacteremia, renal failure, and hepatic failure, all of which can lead to death.¹²

Hepatic abscess is one of rare and fatal complication of TACE and TARE. The incidence rate of hepatic abscess following TACE is 5%. Patients with prior biliary intervention resulting in sphincter of Oddi compromise, such as biliary-enteric anastomosis or sphincterotomy, have an increased incidence of hepatic abscess estimated to be as high as 85%.^{13,14}

Endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) is a combined endoscopic and fluoroscopic procedure in which an upper endoscope is guided into a second part of the duodenum via oral route, making it possible for track of other tools via the major duodenal papilla into the biliary and pancreatic ducts. Contrast material may be injected in these ducts, allowing for radiologic visualization and therapeutic interventions when indicated.¹⁵ Beside the TACE and TARE, cholangitis and hepatic abscess are considered as complication of ERCP.¹⁶

This study will retrospectively evaluate patients with a history of ERCP who had the hepatic abscess or cholangitis following TACE or TARE.

METHOD AND MATERIAL:

It was retrospective chart review study of patients who underwent TACE or TARE after ERCP procedure at the tertiary center, at King Abdulaziz Medical City, between May 2010 and December 2018. After Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval for the study from King Abdullah International Medical Research Centre (KAIMRC), this study was started. Medical records were obtained and reviewed for the following clinical data: age more than 18, gender, diabetes mellitus, BMI, history of gallstone, history of smoking, history of alcohol, time period between ERCP and TACE or TARE procedure. The excluding criteria of the following were applied: hepatic abscess before TACE or TARE and cholangitis before TACE or TARE.

Search of the database will be achieved using the Radiology Information system (RIS) using the following keyword and codes:

TACE AND hepatic abscess OR TACE AND cholangitis OR ERCP AND cholangitis OR ERCP AND hepatic abscess OR TARE AND hepatic abscess OR TARE AND cholangitis.

RESULTS:

A total of nine patients that had undergone TACE or TARE after ERCP were identified. Medical records of these patients were available for review and the data were extracted. All of the cases were conducted in intervention radiology suite. One case was transferred from local hospital where intervention radiology services were not available. The study includes seven male and two female. The mean age of patient is 64.

Five of patients underwent TACE and four patients underwent TARE. The right common femoral artery was punctured under ultrasound guidance

followed by placement of 5-F vascular sheath in all the cases.

At time of procedure, two of the patients were overweight and eight of patients were diagnosed with DM. Three of the patient were diagnosed with gall stones and one of them underwent cholecystectomy. Two patients were smoked and none of the patients were alcoholic. In seven of the cases, the segment 6 was involved and segment 4 & 5 in other two.

Cholangitis was noted in two male patients and hepatic abscess was not found. Based on our finding, one-year survival rate is increased in patients who undergo TACE or TARE. Table 1 summaries our finding.

serial number	AGE	gender	TACE or TARE	alcoholic	smoking	DM	gallstones	BMI	period b/w TACE or TARE and ERCP	hepatic abscess	cholangitis
1	79	Male	TACE	no	no	yes	no	24.65	4 months	No	no
2	52	Male	TACE	no	no	yes	no	24.24	17 months	No	no
3	86	Male	TACE	no	yes	yes	yes	19.81	9 months	No	yes
4	66	Female	TACE	no	no	yes	yes	21	6 months	No	no
5	55	Male	TARE	no	no	yes	no	22.45	13 months	No	No
6	59	Male	TARE	no	no	yes	no	23.72	3 months	No	no
7	62	Female	TARE	no	no	yes	yes	27.51	1 months	No	no
8	24	Male	TARE	no	yes	no	no	20.97	2 months	No	yes
9	93	Male	TACE	no	no	yes	no	27.59	5 years	No	no

DISCUSSION:

The main cause of hepatic abscess related to TACE and TARE is biloma formation. The pathophysiology of biloma formation involves ischemic injury to the peribiliary capillary plexus, which is supplied by branches of the hepatic artery. As a result, the integrity of the biliary tree is disrupted with subsequent biloma formation. Bacterial seeding of these bilomas can produce a hepatic abscess. Moreover, another potential cause of the development of an abscess within the necrotic center is devascularization of hepatic tumor.¹¹ Our chart review study, however, did not find any patient with hepatic abscess.

Our research study found that two patients with cholangitis after retrospective reviewing the clinical note and medical imaging on database. Only one of them developed cholangitis after TACE and another one developed cholangitis after TARE. It was illustrated that acute obstructive cholangitis, due to the migration of completely necrotized tumor fragment after a TACE with obstruction of the distal common bile duct (CBD), is rare.¹⁷

Obesity and DM increase the risk of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease which may lead to cirrhosis.¹⁸ Unfortunately, that can lead to increase the risk of hepatic abscess and cholangitis. Our research study did not find any obese patient at the time of TACE

or TARE procedure. Only two patients were considered as overweight based on BMI value. These two patients did not develop hepatic abscess or cholangitis after TACE or TARE procedure (see appendix). On another hand, our case study found eight diabetic cases. One of them developed cholangitis after TACE procedure and time span between ERCP and TACE is nine months. no Hepatic abscess was not observed in any patient

Alcohol toxicity is the most common cause of hepatitis.¹⁹ In addition, incidence of hepatic abscess and cholangitis is elevated among alcoholics. Our chart review study did not find any patient with a history of alcoholic intake at the time of TACE or TARE procedure.

Smoking might cause a variety of adverse effects on organs that have no direct contact with the smoke itself such as the liver. Smoking increases the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1, IL-6 and TNF- α) that would be involved in liver cell injury.²⁰ Smoking is considered as a risk factor of hepatic abscess and cholangitis.²¹ Our research study show that two patients are smoker. These two patient develop cholangitis after TACE and TARE procedure. One of the developed cholangitis after TACE and underwent ERCP before nine months of this procedure. Another one, however, had cholangitis after TARE and underwent ERCP after two months

A spontaneous (non-traumatic) gallbladder perforation with gallstone disease is not common. Therefore, concomitant development of a liver abscess is a very rare complication observed in such cases.²² Gall stones could obstruct biliary duct resulting in hepatic abscess or cholangitis. Our research study found three patient who had gallstone. Gallstone is noticed in ultrasound image after TACE or TARE procedure. One of these three patients developed cholangitis after TACE procedure and had ERCP before nine months of undergoing TACE.

The limitation of this study is the small number of cases. From the data, there was no available information about whether antibiotics are given or not. The time period between TACE or TARE procedure and outcome complications is not available

In conclusion, cholangitis and hepatic abscess are rare to complication after TACE or TARE procedure in patient with history of ERCP despite other co-morbidities. For the future directions, a case-control and large-scale study should be conducted in order to investigate the risk factors of having cholangitis and hepatic abscess after

complication of TACE or TARE procedure in a patient with history of ERCP .

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